

CONDUCTIVE AND STRONG NANOCOMPOSITES BASED ON CELLULOSE NANOFIBRILS AND CARBON NANOTUBES

Alireza Hajian and Lars A. Berglund

Wallenberg Wood Science Center, Department of Fiber and Polymer Technology, KTH Royal
Institute of Technology, Stockholm, Sweden

Email: hajian@kth.se, web page: <http://wwsc.se/>

ABSTRACT

Single-wall carbon nanotubes (SWNTs) can be dispersed with the aid of cellulose nanofibrils (CNF) in aqueous medium. The dispersions have high stability and quality that can be utilized into self-assembly of functional composites having high electrical conductivity and strength. The composites were then carefully analyzed in terms of their mechanical and electrical properties as well as dispersion quality.

Keywords: Carbon Nanotubes, Nanocellulose, Nanocomposite, Electrical Conductivity, Mechanical Properties

INTRODUCTION

Since the discovery of carbon nanotubes, a lot of attention has been towards this material due to its superior mechanical, thermal and electrical properties. CNTs have been used in many applications such as electronic devices, sensors, functional composites, coatings, etc. CNTs can add electrical conductivity and strength to the composites. [1] However they must be well-dispersed from bundles into individualized tubes in the matrix. Achieving a well-dispersed state of carbon nanotubes in a matrix has always been a challenge in order to exploit their best properties in the composite. The main routes to reach this aim have always been through chemical functionalization of carbon nanotubes [2] or using surfactant [3] both of which have their own drawback on the electrical and mechanical performance of the pristine carbon nanotubes. The most applied polymeric matrices for carbon nanotubes are synthetic polymers such as epoxy, [4] whereas as an alternative to synthetic polymers, polymers from renewable resources can be applied.

One of the most abundant polymers from a renewable resource is cellulose nanofibrils (CNF), having the dimensions of above 1 μm in length and 5-15 nm in diameter with crystal modulus of above 100 GPa. According to chemically modifiable surface, high aspect ratio and relatively inexpensive methods of their production, cellulose nanofibers have shown great potential in various applications including nanoreinforcement in composites, transparent coatings, lbl deposition for multilayer functional surfaces, etc. [5, 6]

It has been shown that functional composites can be made with CNF such as transparent random-network nanopaper. [7] The discovery that CNF is able to well-disperse as-prepared SWNTs opens the possibility to make such nanopapers having high electrical conductivity benefiting from lack of surfactant and no side-wall functionalization on the nanotubes. [8] In this work a comparison (in terms

of mechanical performance and electrical conductivity) between this work and the previous conventional methods of dispersing CNT (chemical functionalization or using surfactant) in CNF (as matrix) is depicted. One example is the conductive composites made from Tempo-oxidized CNF and carboxylic acid functionalized CNT [9] and another example is the composites from tempo-oxidized CNF and acid phosphate ester of ethoxylated nonylphenol (NPPE) as the surfactant for aqueous CNT dispersion. [10]

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Preparation of random-network nanopaper

CNF from softwood sulphite pulp having carboxyl groups on the surface (provided by Innventia AB, Sweden) was purified by dilution to 1 g/L dispersion of CNF followed by shear mixing using ultra turrax IKA T25 at 14000 rpm for about 15 min, probe sonication in ice-bath and centrifugation Beckman Coulter J2 at 4500 rpm for 1 h where about 80% of the supernatant was taken out. In the next step, untreated high-pressure carbon monoxide disproportionation (HiPco) SWNT was added to the dispersion, followed by probe sonication in ice-bath and centrifugation at 20000 g for 1 h and around 80% of the supernatant was taken. The composite nanopapers were made via vacuum filtration of the dispersions using hydrophobic polyvinyl difluoride (PVDF) Millipore membrane filters having 0.65 μm pore size followed by using a sheet former (Rapid Köthen, RK3A-KWT PTI).

Characterization (electrical conductivity and mechanical performance)

The electrical conductivity of the nanopapers was measured using Solartron SI1287 with graphite electrodes on the edges of the paper (four-point probe van der Pauw set-up). The mechanical properties of the nanopapers were measured using tensile test under controlled conditions (23°C and 50% relative humidity). The specimens were cut into rectangles with the dimensions of 50 mm in length, 5 mm in width and average thickness of 10 μm . 5 specimens from each composition were tested using Universal Material Testing Machine Instron 5944 equipped with 500 N load cell with initial strain rate of 10 %/min that gives cross-head speed of 5 mm/min.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

CNF-SWNTs dispersions were prepared as described in materials and methods. A well-dispersed carbon nanotubes in the dispersion is shown under TEM (figure 1) and then the nanopapers were prepared and their mechanical and electrical performance is compared with the works by Salajkova et al. [10] and Koga et al. [9] as two examples of the composites with same constituents, but different dispersion preparations (surfactant-assisted dispersion and chemical functionalization of the nanotubes, respectively).

Figure 1: TEM image of NFC-SWNTs dispersion dried on carbon-coated copper grid, scale bar shows 500 nm

In the work by Salajkova et al. nanopapers were made with NPPE dispersed MWNTs mixed with tempo-oxidized CNF (TOCN) in different weight ratios. This work showed with increasing multi-walled carbon nanotubes (MWNTs) content in the composite, the modulus and strength of the nanopapers decrease and these values reach 7.72 GPa and 183 MPa respectively for the nanopaper with 9.1 wt% MWNTs. [10] This drop in modulus and strength compared to CNF nanopaper can be related to the presence of more NPPE surfactant with more MWNTs in the structures which disrupts the mechanical performance of already-strong CNF nanopaper (table 1), as interfacial slippage is vital in strength and modulus of the composites in parallel with good dispersion. [11] Moreover, the inner tubes in MWNTs do not play a significant role in increasing tensile properties in the composite and so they are considered as bigger particles with lower aspect ratio compared with SWNTs and so this needs to be considered beside the effect of surfactant in the MWNTs composites to compare their properties. [12]

Table 1: Tensile test results of CNF -CNT composites for comparison, (see the references) [8, 9, 10]

Sample	Modulus (GPa)	Strength (MPa)
~10 wt% SWNTs	9.5 ^[9]	100 ^[9]
~10 wt% SWNTs	11.2 ^[8]	213 ^[8]
9.1 wt% MWNTs	7.72 ^[10]	183 ^[10]

In the work by Koga et al., carboxylic acid functionalized SWNTs were mixed with TOCN cellulose nanofibers and the resulting composites were characterized. [9] In this work, there has also been generally a drop in modulus and strength with increasing nanotube content which can be due to surface functionalization of the SWNTs that resulted in reducing the length of the nanotubes (table 1).

In our work, there exists the same trend that generally with increasing CNT content in the composite, the strength and Young's modulus decrease, too. However, this decrease in strength and modulus is not very significant and the main goal here was to apply the most possible well-dispersed SWNTs in the CNF matrix to increase electrical conductivity without significantly destroying the mechanical performance of the already strong CNF nanopaper. Furthermore, in our work, the mechanical results do not follow the superposition of the properties, since there is a slight increase in both modulus and strength with addition of only 3 wt% SWNTs to the CNF nanopaper and then drops with more CNT content. There is 10% and 29% drop in modulus and strength of the nanopaper with addition of 10 wt% SWNTs. This drop in modulus and strength with more CNT loadings can be related to the tendency of more aggregate formation with more CNT in the composite. [8]

Figure 2: Optical image from CNF -SWNTs 10 wt% (our work) showing semi-transparency of the nanopaper

Comparing the electrical conductivity of the nanopapers shows that the conductivity of the composites increases by increasing CNT content, while the value in our work shows the highest conductivity reported for CNF-CNT composites that can be according to better-dispersed CNTs in the composite. In the work by Salajkova et al. where NPPE was used as surfactant to disperse MWNTs, the conductivity of the composite reaches the maximum of 0.001 S/cm with around 17 wt% MWNTs. This can be explained by the existence of surfactant that limits the nanotube-nanotube carrier hopping. In the work by Koga et al. where carboxylic acid functionalized SWNTs were used, the electrical conductivity reaches around 10 S/cm for 12 V% (~ 16 wt%) of nanotubes in the composite and the electrical conductivity of 120 S/cm for the buckypaper reference. This relatively low conductivity can be due to destroying of the electronic network of the CNTs via side-wall functionalization.

Table 2: Highest reported electrical conductivity for CNF -CNT composites from the data of three references compared in this work (see the references) [8, 9, 10]

Sample	Conductivity (S/cm)
16 wt% SWNTs	10 ^[9]
~43 wt% SWNTs	174 ^[8]
~16 wt% MWNTs	0.001 ^[10]

CONCLUSIONS

CNF is highly efficient in dispersing SWNTs without the use of surfactant or functionalization of the SWNTs. CNF-SWNTs nanopapers with different compositions were successfully prepared and characterized. The nanopaper with 43 wt% SWNTs showed an electrical conductivity as high as 174 S/cm. In general, the mechanical properties were favorable. The nanopaper with 10 wt% SWNT showed 11.2 GPa modulus and 213 MPa strength. CNF-SWNTs nanopapers can be used in many applications such as sensors, supercapacitors, transparent electrodes, energy-storage devices, etc.

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